

**RECYCLING FIBRES
FROM
POST-CONSUMER
WOOD WASTE
INTO INSULATION
PRODUCTS**

**PROJECT INNOVATION
FACTSHEET**

Contributing to EU's circular bioeconomy, reintegrating post-consumer wood waste into production helps optimise wood use, extend product lifecycle, store carbon and reduce dependence on virgin wood.

APPLICATIONS

Wood fibre thermal insulation materials are used in the building envelope to support stable indoor temperature, helping reduce energy use and improve comfort. They are available as:

- **Rigid boards** for sarking and external insulation of pitched roofs and façades, offering strong thermo-acoustic performance and high summer heat delay.
- **Flexible boards** for internal insulation of roof rafters, walls and partitions. Easy to cut and install, with a compressible fit that adapts to irregular spaces.
- **Loose-fill insulation** for walls and attics, cost-effective and easy to install, helping to seal thermal bridges.

ACHIEVEMENTS

- **Rigid boards:**
 - 115kg/m³: meet specifications with up to 25% fibres from post-consumer fibreboard or up to 100% using well sorted and cleaned fibres from post-consumer solid wood.
 - 200Kg/m³: incorporation of recycled fibres reduces the mechanical properties too much to meet the specifications.
- **Flexible boards:**
 - Meet specifications with up to 50% fibres from post-consumer fibreboard and up to 100% using well sorted and cleaned fibres post-consumer solid wood.
- **Loose-fill insulation:**
 - Wall cavities: meets specifications with up to 25% fibres from post-consumer fibreboard or up to 100% using well sorted and cleaned fibres from post-consumer solid wood.
 - Attics: fibres from post-consumer fibreboard are not suitable while up to 50% well sorted and cleaned fibres from post-consumer solid wood could be considered.

NEXT STEPS

- Improve input quality and process control, especially to reduce dust from post-consumer fibreboard fibres.
- Scale up to industrial scale.

PARTNERS

CONTACTS

SOPREMA

Laurent Bedel

Insulation R&D Director

lbedel@soprema.fr

 soprema.com

SLU SWEDISH UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

Department of Forest Biomaterials and Technology - Division of Wood Science and Technology | Uppsala, Sweden

Stergios Adamopoulos

Professor, Wood Science

stergios.adamopoulos@slu.se

 slu.se

[More information :](#)

 [EcoReFibre on LinkedIn](#)

 ecorefibre.eu

This document reflects the authors' views only and neither the Agency nor the Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Funded by
the European Union

Photo credits: Soprema, Sonae Arauco, InnovaWood.
Layout: Fovéa création.